

COMPARATIVE ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF RAINFED AND IRRIGATED COTTON IN AKOLA DISTRICT

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken in Akola district of Vidarbha region. The cotton crop was selected for the present study. Two tehsils from Akola district were selected for the present study from each tehsil, three villages were selected. The schedule was designed for primary data collection keeping in view the objectives of the present study. The data pertains for the year 2023-24. To accomplish the objectives, of the present study simple tabular analysis was used. The resource use efficiency in cotton cultivation was analysed by using Cobb-Douglous production function. production function for rainfed cotton indicate that out of seven selected variables human labour, bullock labour, and phosphorous contributed significantly with total contribution of 92 per cent explained by selected variables. The numerical value for MVP for rainfed cotton was 0.19, 0.26, -0.05 for human labour, bullock labour, and phosphorous respectively. It revealed that the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was found to be 92, that means 92 per cent variation in output was jointly explained by the selected seven independent variables. Human labour, bullock labour and phosphorous Kg/ha are significantly contributed. . It can also be stated as, one per cent increase in the use of total human labour (X_1), bullock labour (x_2), and two per cent in phosphorous will increase the yield by 0.36, 0.23, and 0.40 per cent, respectively. For irrigated cotton cultivation coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was found to be 0.98, that means 98 per cent variation in output was jointly explained by the selected seven independent variables. Human labour and phosphorous contributed significantly. It can also be stated as, one percent increase in human labour and phosphorous will increase the yield by 1.30 and 0.19 per cent respectively. The numerical value of MVP for irrigated cotton was 0.83 and 0.15 for Bullock labour and phosphorous.

Keywords: Resource use efficiency, Production function, Marginal value product.

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium spp.*) belongs to the family Malvaceae. Its primary centre of origin is India. Among the fibre crops, cotton is the most important fibre crop grown since ancient times in the country. The existence of cotton is found in Rig Veda written around 1500 BC. India remained the chief producer of cotton until 1500 BC. Cotton is basic need of cloth, human being which is required right from his birth to death. It is a gift of nature providing fibre for clothing since time immemorial. It is one of the most important commercial cash crops besides serving as a source of natural fibre and oil and providing raw material to the textile and oil industry. It plays a vital role in Indian economy is concern. For many centuries, the cotton plant was known outside India through 'travellers tales'. It is one of the important sources of foreign exchange, it is also known as "White Gold."

The major cotton producing countries are China (6,423,000 tons), India (6,162,000 tons), United States (3,181,000 tons), Brazil (2,341,000 tons), Pakistan (980,000 tons) (source – World Population Review). India is second largest producer of cotton in the world after China as per the USDA. The production of cotton in India in 2021-22 is 312.03 lakh bales. Cotton is important commercial crop of India. Maharashtra (80.25 lakh bales) is second leading state in cotton production after Gujrat (91.83 lakh bales), the state accounts for 25per cent (65 million kgs) of the country's total cotton production. The major cotton growing states are Gujrat (91.83 lakh bales), Maharashtra (80.25 lakh bales), Telangana (53.25 lakh bales), Rajasthan (27.12 lakh bales), Karnataka (21.04 lakh bales). (Source – Gov- Press information Bureau). Vidarbha, located in the eastern part of Maharashtra, is a significant cotton-producing region in India. The region contributes about 30% of India's cotton crop. However, the average cotton yield in Vidarbha is around 300 kg per hectare, which is lower than the national average of 500 kg per hectare and the world average of 700 kg per hectare. (International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR))

In Maharashtra the area under cotton is 42 lakh hectares, production 85 lakh bales of cotton and yield 343.48kg/ha. The 80per cent cotton is grown in Khandesh, Vidarbha Marathwada regions. The major districts are Jalgaon, Akola, Yawatmal, Osmanabad, Nanded, Aurangabad, Wardha, Nagpur, Amravati and Buldhana. In Akola District the Area under cotton is 1517 hectares, production 3673.8 metric tons and productivity is 411.7 kg/ha (2021-22) (source- S.D.A.O, Akola).

Importance of study

The study analysed resource use efficiency in rainfed and irrigated cotton cultivation. This analysis is crucial because cotton is commercially important for growers in Akola district. The study

focused on examining the current utilization level of various inputs such as labour, seed, machineries, plant nutrients. It emphasized the commercial importance of cotton crop in the specific region, suggesting that cotton is grown over a large area in the district and are considered a profitable crop. Therefore, this study was planned with the following Objective

To estimate the resource use efficiency of rainfed and irrigated cotton.

Methodology

The present study was conducted in Akola district of the Vidarbha region, focusing on cotton cultivation. Two tehsils from Akola district were included in the study, with three villages selected from each tehsil, total 120 farmers were selected for this study. The data collection schedule was designed to align with the study's objectives and pertains to the year 2023-24. A simple tabular analysis was used to achieve the study's objectives, and the resource use efficiency was examined using cobb-douglous production function.

Method of analysis**Production function analysis**

The transformation of inputs into output is described by the production function. The production function can be specified as follows.

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)$$

Where Y is the per hectare output of a particular crop with a given set of inputs X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n per hectare. In simple words production function can be defined as "Mathematical and technical relationship existing between the input and output. In functional analysis, it would be essential to choose an appropriate form of production function taking into consideration the data. The Cobb-Douglas type of production function has been wide zer 66/343 tit function in the economic analysis. The Cobb-Douglas type of production function was used specified as follows.

$$Y = ax_1^{b_1} x_2^{b_2} x_3^{b_3} x_4^{b_4} x_5^{b_5} x_6^{b_6} x_7^{b_7}$$

Where,

Y = Yield in quintals per hectare

a = Intercept

$b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5, b_6, b_7$ = Regression coefficient of the respective factor as below:

X_1 = Human labour (days)

X_2 = Bullock labour (days)

X_3 = Machine labour (days)

X_4 = Seeds (kgs)

X_5 = Expenditure on Nitrogen (Kg.)

X_6 = Expenditure on Phosphorus (Kg.)

X_7 = Expenditure on Potassium (Kg.)

Cobb-Douglas production function as given above was estimated for input-output data to study contribution of variables and resource productivity.

Marginal value product to factor cost relation:

The marginal value product of particular resource represents "the expected addition to the total output caused by an addition of one unit of that resource while other inputs are held constant.

$$MVP = b_1 \cdot Gm(Y)/Gm(x_1)$$

Cobb Douglas production function for irrigated and rainfed cotton

Sr.No.	Particulars	Rainfed	Irrigation
1.	Constant (Intercept)	-0.19 (0.27)	-1.13 (0.19)
a.	Human Labour	0.36** (0.19)	1.30** (0.10)
b.	Bullock Labour	0.23* (0.093)	0.20 (0.06)
c.	Machine	-0.09 (0.092)	-0.04 (0.16)
d.	Seed	0.16 (0.11)	-0.15 (0.19)
e.	N	-0.06 (0.17)	0.06 (0.07)
f.	P	0.40* (0.23)	-0.19* (0.09)
g.	K	-0.07 (0.05)	0.00 (0.03)
2.	Coefficient of Determination(R^2)	0.92	0.98

* Significance at 5 per cent level.

** Significance at 1 per cent level

Marginal value product to factor cost ratio for irrigated and rainfed cotton

Sr.no	Particulars	Rainfed	Irrigation
1	Human Labour	0.19	0.83
2	Bullock Labour	0.26	0.54
3	Machine	-0.17	-0.08
4	Seed	4.53	-0.73
5	N	-0.01	0.04
6	P	-0.05	-0.15
7	K	0.01	0.00

It was observed from table 4.1 and 4.2 production function for rainfed cotton indicate that out of seven selected variables human labour, bullock labour, and phosphorous contributed significantly with total contribution of 92 per cent explained by selected variables. The numerical value for MVP for rainfed cotton was 0.19, 0.26, -0.05 for human labour, bullock labour, and phosphorous respectively. It revealed that the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was found to be 92, that means 92 per cent variation in output was jointly explained by the selected seven independent variables. Human labour, bullock labour and phosphorous Kg/ha are significantly contributed. It can also be stated as, one per cent increase in the use of total human labour (X_1), bullock labour (x_2), and two per cent in phosphorous will increase the yield by 0.36, 0.23, and 0.40 per cent, respectively. For irrigated cotton cultivation coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was found to be 0.98, that means 98 per cent variation in output was jointly explained by the selected seven independent variables. Human labour and phosphorous contributed significantly. It can also be stated as, one percent increase in human labour and phosphorous will increase the yield by 1.30 and 0.19 per cent respectively. The numerical value of MVP for irrigated cotton was 0.83 and 0.15 for Bullock labour and phosphorous.

Conclusion

Production function for rainfed cotton indicate that out of seven selected variables human labour, bullock labour, and phosphorous contributed significantly with total contribution of 92 per cent explained by selected variables.

Where,

B = The elasticity of the output with respect to input X

Gm (x) = Geometric mean of input X

Gm (Y) = Geometric mean of output Y

Result and discussion

Keeping in the view the objectives of the present study, the data were analysed by using suitable techniques.

It can be revealed that the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was found to be 92, that means 92 per cent variation in output was jointly explained by the selected seven independent variables.

The one per cent increase in the use of total human labour (X_1), bullock labour (x_2), and two per cent in phosphorous will increase the yield by 0.36, 0.23, and 0.40 per cent, respectively.

For irrigated cotton cultivation coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was found to be 0.98, that means 98 per cent variation in output was jointly explained by the selected seven independent variables. Human labour and phosphorous contributed significantly.

The one percent increase in human labour and phosphorous will increase the yield by 1.30 and 0.19 per cent respectively.

The numerical value of MVP for irrigated cotton was 0.83 and 0.15 for Bullock labour and phosphorous.

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